

COGNITIVE-DISCURSIVE MODEL OF A NEWS EVENT AND ITS INVARIANT-VARIANT MEDIA REPRESENTATION

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Annotation: In the domestic scientific school of media linguistics and journalism, various differentiating features are offered: by the specific purpose and nature of the object in the publication (facts as direct events of reality and objects of reflected reality), by the scale of coverage of reality (the breadth of coverage of reality, the scale of conclusions and generalizations), by the nature of literary -stylistic means (linguistic ways of reflecting reality).

Introduction

Substantive features - the subject of display, target setting, methods of researching the subject - are based on the functional division of the genres of periodicals, in which, along with analytical and artistic journalistic, informational ones are singled out [Kim, 2011, p. 242]. The latter include groups of "texts-carriers of operational information that allow the audience to constantly monitor the most significant events in a particular field of activity" [Tertychny, 2011, p. 13-23], in particular, this is a note, report, reportage, interview, announcement, blitz survey, etc., and they are united by such features as accuracy, clarity, brevity of information presentation. Note that the proposed system of formats for operational news texts ("texts reporting new, previously unknown information to the reader" [Fundamentals of the creative activity of a journalist, 2000, p. 120]) corresponds to the idea of a news message aimed at solving the information problem of media discourse receiving a media representation in the genre of an informational note, article, essay, reportage.

An information note and an article are considered to be the central forms of the information genre [Slinina, 2015 and others]. They are called classical genres of the press, since they developed along with the development of professional journalism, and are distinguished by a clear definition of communicative functions in media discourse, the rigor of formal and content structures, and a standard composition that allows telescopic transformations of information blocks when presenting socially significant events. The telescopic nature of the composition is manifested in two models - full and truncated. The complete compositional model of the English-language text of a news message consists of a title, an introductory sentence, and the main part of the text that verbally embodies the cognitive-discursive model of the news. The classic news note is the shortest and minimally sufficient form of informing. Its textual volume is

limited, it may consist of one or more sentences that correspond to the cognitive-discursive model of the news: what happened, where, when, with whom. In addition, an indication of the source of information is required. An informational article, unlike a news article, allows the inclusion of details of the event, explanations of the causes and consequences (how and why it happened, what led to it, etc.).

Significant for the two informational genres is the compositional structure of the text, which is usually characterized by the “inverted pyramid model” or “iceberg” [Hodkinson, 2013, etc.]. Despite the desire for accuracy in information, the facts and stages of the event are not transmitted in the chronological order of the narrative; the most important information is reported first, then the details and less important, but figurative information follow in descending order of importance. This model of information in blocks is very convenient for news agencies and news publications, since it allows you to easily transform the text - shorten it from the end, break it into semantic parts that are placed on different pages of the printed publication or used in electronic publications that are hypertextual and multimodal [Slinina, 2015; Ilinova, 2013].

Conclusion

Note that the perception of information in printed and electronic versions is different. Historically, the printed text in periodicals has assumed a linear reading, but the increase and acceleration of the information flow has led to the fact that readers have become less likely to read all the articles in the publication. In modern electronic news publications, linear perception of information is not initially assumed. The text can be associated with other texts, other semiotic systems of signs (photos, graphics, videos). The reader is encouraged to non-linear reading of information. In the modern world, skimming and selective reading prevail, so journalism has developed various ways to hold the reader's attention and organize navigation through the news discourse. These methods are: creating headlines that are unusual in style or form, highlighting text, breaking the text into compositional blocks and placing them on different pages of the publication, using illustrative material, etc. At the same time, despite the increase in technical capabilities to attract the reader's attention, news traditional forms of the information genre still exist - a news note and a news article

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